

DIGITAL LIBRARY: THE NEED OF NEXT GENERATION 21ST LIBRARIANSHIP

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Abstract

According to Wikipedia "A digital library is a special library with a focused collection of digital objects that can include text, visual material, audio material, video material, stored as electronic media formats (as opposed to print, microform, or other media), along with means for organizing, storing, and retrieving the files and media contained in the library collection. Digital libraries can vary immensely in size and scope, and can be maintained by individuals, organizations, or affiliated with established physical library buildings or institutions, or with academic institutions".¹

The present paper is focus on the concept of digital library, their types, features, and services offer by them.

Keywords: Digital Library, World Digital Library, Digital Library of Indian, Science Digital Library

Introduction

According to Wikipedia "The term digital libraries was first popularized by the NSF/DARPA/NASA Digital Libraries Initiative in 1994. These draw heavily on Vannevar Bush's essay As We May Think (1945), which set out a vision not in terms of technology, but user experience".²

There is no specific definition of digital library which will comprehensively discuss the concept, but generalize statement says, number of computers connected with Internet connection with each other and store vast amount of digital material on virtual base may be called as a digital library. Earlier it was refer as an electronic library, virtual library, and library without wall and now it is popularize as a digital library.

According to Clifford Lynch, once of the leading scholars in the area of digital library research, it is not. Lynch (1997:52) states: "One sometimes hears the Internet characterized as the world's library for the digital age. This description does not stand up under even casual examination. The Internet and particularly its collection of multimedia resources known as the World Wide Web was not designed to support the organized publication and retrieval of information as libraries are. It has evolved into what might be thought of as a chaotic repository for the collective output of the world's digital "printing presses.".... ..In short, the Net is not a digital library"³

Research Problem

- Are the users exactly know the concept of digital library

- Whether the various type of digital library create awareness or inculcate the reading habit

Objective of the Study

- To identify whether the digital library have a positive impact on users
- To find out most preferred digital library e-resources

Hypothesis Formulation

- Null hypothesis – Users consider digital library is not useful for learning process.
- Alternative hypothesis – Users consider digital library is important for learning process.

Significant of the Study

- The present study will be useful for users those are not aware of digital library concept.
- The study has been focus more on various digital libraries which provide descriptive information of them.

World Digital Library

The World Digital Library (WDL) is a project of the U.S. Library of Congress, carried out with the support of the United Nations Educational, Cultural and Scientific Organization (UNESCO), and in cooperation with libraries, archives, museums, educational institutions, and international organizations from around the world.

The WDL makes available on the Internet, free of charge and in multilingual format, significant primary materials from all countries and cultures.

The principal objectives of the WDL are to:

- Promote international and intercultural understanding;
- Expand the volume and variety of cultural content on the Internet;
- Provide resources for educators, scholars, and general audiences;
- Build capacity in partner institutions to narrow the digital divide within and between countries.⁴

Collection Statistics of World Digital Library

Table - 1

Sr. No.	Particular	Nos.
1	Country Represented	193
2	Language Represented	131
3	Downloadable files	665887
4	Searchable content pages	215619

Table - 2

Sr. No.	Particular	Items	Files
1	Print, Photographs	7011	10579
2	News paper	2689	9486
3	Books	1417	369516
4	Manuscripts	1323	247304
5	Maps	934	7195
6	Journals	308	18610
7	Motion Pictures	30	36
8	Sound recording	13	13
Total		13725	662739

(Table-1and2 - Source – World Digital Library <https://www.wdl.org/en/statistics/>)

Digital Library of India

The Digital Library of India is hosted by Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore in co-operation with CMU, IIT-Hyderabad, NSF, ENRNET, MCIT for the Government of India.

“Digital Library of India (DLI) is a digital collection of freely accessible rare books collected from various libraries in India. DLI project started in early 2000 with the vision to archive all the significant literary, artistic and scientific works of mankind and to preserve digitally and make them available freely for every one over Internet for education, study, appreciation and for future generations. As a first step in realizing this vision, it is proposed to create the Digital Library with a free-to-read, searchable collection of one million books, predominantly in Indian languages. The Project was initiated by the Office of the Principal Scientific Advisor to the Government of India and subsequently taken over by the Department of Electronics and Information Technology (DeitY), Ministry of Communications and Information Technology (MCIT), Govt. of India. The idea was also to create a test bed for researchers to improve scanning techniques, optical character recognition, intelligent indexing and in general to promote Indian Language Technology Research”.⁵

According to Digital Library of India “It has currently 550,619 books available with 191,677,823 pages (191.657 Million). There are 200,542 books comprising of 56,458,745 pages of Indian languages available on DLI website”.

Digital Library have been established Scanning Centre across the part of India, where retrieval of information from difference source of digital material work has been done by them

on request from users. The setup of digital library is based on DSpace Software which is one of the known Open Source Software kinds of Repository Application to many.

According to Wikipedia, “The scanning of Indian language books has created an opportunity for developing Indian language optical character recognition (OCR) software. The publications are mainly in PDF or QuickTime format. Because of copyright laws, the texts are all out of copyright and therefore not sources for current information, but rather useful for history and background. As of 2006 (November 10), DLI had scanned 84,895 titles”.⁶

The library is the social institutions and always connected to people and learners with source of information required by them. At the same time Digital Library offers unlimited services to users. Users’ involvement in process of education system play vital role and it is observed that, advance state of the art technology with Digital Library has positive impact on learning process.

National Science Digital Library of India

“National Science Digital Library (NSDL) aims at providing comprehensive S&T information to students of science, engineering and technology in the country. Begun as a Tenth Five Year Plan Network Project of Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), NSDL is the only one of its kind that provides curriculum based content to address the information needs of the undergraduate students of science. The content creation and development for NSDL has gone through rigorous procedures to make available quality content for the students. Authored by eminent teachers and validated by renowned faculty in Indian universities and colleges, NSDL envisages bringing finest content to the students. The discussion forum has been provided for interactions amongst NSDL users”.⁷

“National Institute of Science Communication and Information Resources (NISCAIR) came into existence on 30 September 2002 with the merger of National Institute of Science Communication (NISCOM) and Indian National Scientific Documentation Centre (INSDOC). Both NISCOM and INSDOC, the two premier institutes of the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), were devoted to dissemination and documentation of S&T information. NISCOM had been in existence for the last six decades (first as two Publication Units of CSIR, which were merged to form the Publications Division, which was later renamed as Publications & Information Directorate and in 1996, as NISCOM). Over the years, NISCOM diversified its activities, and through a host of its information products, comprising research and popular science journals, encyclopaedic publications, monographs, books, and information services, it had been reaching out to researchers, students,

entrepreneurs, industrialists, agriculturists, policy planners and also the common man. INSDOC came into being in 1952 and was engaged in providing S&T information and documentation services through myriad activities such as abstracting and indexing, design and development of databases, translation, library automation, providing access to international information sources, human resource development, consultancy services in setting up modern library-cum-information centres. INSDOC was also host to the National Science Library and the SAARC Documentation Centre.

Now, with the formation of NISCAIR, all the above multi-faceted activities have been amalgamated, making NISCAIR, an institute capable of serving the society using modern IT infrastructure in a more effective manner and taking up new ventures in the field of science communication, dissemination and S&T information management systems and services. Broadly the core activity of NISCAIR will be to collect/store, publish and disseminate S&T information through a mix of traditional and modern means, which will benefit different segments of society".⁸

Types of Digital Library

- Stand-alone Digital Library (SDL) – It is also referring as a self contained which includes edited, generated, scanned, digitized, purchased digital materials, and several collection usually localized on server for eg. Library of Congress, National Digital Library, Internet Public Library, Snunit, etc.
- Federated Digital Library (FDL) – It is referring confederated or networked library which contains many autonomous libraries, usually heterogeneous repository connected via network for eg. Networked Computer Science Technical Reference Library, Online Computer Literacy Center, etc.
- Harvested Digital Library (HDL) – It is also referring as distributed digital library does not have to contain objects, just metadata/summaries but it has characteristic of digital library for eg. SourceBank, ArticleCenral.Com, Harvest/Katsir, OAL, etc.

Sample list of Digital Library

- Library of Congress - <https://www.loc.gov/>
- National Science Digital Library - <https://nsdl.co.in/>
- Internet Public Library - www.ipl.org/
- California Digital Library - www.cdlib.org
- British Library - www.bl.uk ›

- Einstein Archives Online - www.alberteinstein.info/

Conclusion and Suggestions

The Digital library around the world are have been working on how to meets continues changes in users demands and their requirements which need to be addressed first. Here, we have to think before offer digital service to users, many changes have been taken place in last decades as far as collection, services, materials are concern, but there is need to be awareness programme for usres, skill programme to staff, participative activities, and user-friendly access to existing resources which will create positive impact of users learning process.

Based on above finding there are some suggestions are made those are;

- To inculcate reading habits amongst the learners by changing role of library from collection to connection with users.
- To provide further advanced state of the art IT based services with help of digital library.
- Improvisation of existing system need to be done on frequently basis and its should meet users needs.

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